

Adaptation and deployment of the "La Forêt Bouge" toolbox

Introduction

In the years leading up to the project, Brittany's forestry and wood industry was involved in the development of three main markets (construction, packaging and wood energy), as well as in wood processing using sawmills, and in ensuring the sustainability of timber resources through the Breizh Forêt Bois initiative. There is a need for structuring action, particularly in forestry and forestry work. This will require a better understanding of the sector's activities and needs, in order to facilitate contacts with the other links in the chain (owners and trainers) and to set up appropriate training and support for innovation. The aim of the project was to strengthen the position of forestry professionals in Brittany, with a view to optimising the supply chain. In particular, this work has involved adapting and deploying the "la forêt bouge" toolbox, with the aim of adapting it to the regional context of Brittany, as well as improving its functionality by adding new modules where necessary.

Methodology and results

The "La forêt bouge" service site targets forest owners and professionals in the forestry and wood industry. It aims to promote contact between the various stakeholders (private, economic or institutional) in the forestry sector. This tool enables them to facilitate procedures, forest management, and silvicultural operations by encouraging the grouping of management and/or land ownership. It aims to develop the mobilisation of wood in private forests through innovative services and access to news and popularisation documents. Stakeholders can create their own account and access tailored, individualised services more quickly. This project is a collaborative effort involving all the players in the forestry and wood industry. It is based on three strategies, firstly by defining a common foundation, then by testing the adaptation of the tool in four pilot regions and finally by implementing the tool in all the regions of France. The adaptation of the tool in the "Pays de la Loire" pilot region was carried out by the Sylviconnect operational group. The deployment of the "La Forêt bouge" tool was only able to be carried out imperfectly in the final year of the project, due to its dependency on national deployment and decisions. Nevertheless, all the editorial work and the creation of content, particularly on prices (for wood in forests and for forestry work) and good operating practices, have enabled significant progress to be made in the consultation of stakeholders in Brittany.

Lessons learned

The development of the La Forêt bouge platform and, in particular, its regional office in Brittany, will ultimately provide a much better link between forest owners and forestry companies. Until now, forest owners simply didn't have access to the contact details of professionals depending on the type of work they needed.

This tool, coupled with the database of professionals in the sector, will make it easier to put people in touch with each other and should help to improve the management or re-management of small forest plots. The platform also has a strong educational dimension, providing a wealth of information about the forest, forestry operations and the regulations that apply, as well as disseminating best practices. In a few years' time, this platform should be the key tool for forest owners and players in the industry.

The process has been slow to get off the ground because of delays in development. Some of the functionalities developed at the regional level in Brittany are used as references at the national level. The meetings that have been held have also helped to build a collective driving force on the subject. However, all these actions need to be sustained over time if they are to have a real long-term impact on the forest.

Figure 1. Presentation of the "La Forêt Bouge" toolbox website.

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Further information

<https://www.xn-reseau-national-agricultures-ruralits-bkd.fr/centre-de-ressources/projets/sylviconnect-une-sylviculture-durable-et-performante-pour-la-bretagne>

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